

Gender Gap in Literacy- A Case Study of Malda, West Bengal

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Abstract

The gender gap in education has evoked from several social and cultural beliefs pertinent to a region and results in huge differences in economic spin offs of that region. The study area is chosen to be Malda, a very prominent and rich in heritage district of the state of West Bengal. The major objectives of the study are to find out the disparity in literacy rate and availability of education among the males and females of the region. This consisted of the collection of secondary data and information from various sources. The study depicts that literacy rate is overall low in the concerned district with a huge gap in literacy between male and female. The disparity in male-female population of the blocks is calculated by means of Sopher Index and the fifteen CD Blocks of the region are divided into high, low and medium disparity zones. High disparity in literacy among male and female is found in the CD Blocks of Bamangola, Habibpur, Manikchak, Kaliachak III, Gazole, Harishchandrapur I. Several contributing factors have been identified and measures have been suggested likewise. Though several schemes have been initiated by both the Central and State Governments, yet the goodness is far from being reached to every household. Education of women plays a pivotal role in women empowerment and narrowing gender gap. Thus, corrective decisions are to be taken for the overall collective growth of the nation which requires to learn about the participation of males and females in the economy.

Keywords: gender gap, literacy, disparity, corrective measures, awareness.

Introduction

The popular definition of literacy in the mainstream dictionaries has been the ability to read and write. However, this traditional concept has changed at contemporary times when the word is used to embrace a wide range of perceptions associated with the thought process manifested by this ability. The conventional concept of literacy is bounded by the skills of reading, writing and learning. But communication in an increasingly digital, text-mediated, information-rich and fast-changing world. Yet, in most parts of the world, the discrepancy remains on the attainment of education between males and females. The gender gap in education has

evoked from several social and cultural beliefs pertinent to a region and results in huge differences in economic spin offs of that region.

Study Area

Malda, being a very prominent district of the state of West Bengal, covers an area of 3733 square kilometres. It is bounded to the north by Uttar Dinajpur, to the south by Murshidabad, Bangladesh to the east and Jharkhand in the west. Malda shares an international border with Bangladesh and is the entry point of Siliguri from south Bengal- thus it has a central position in the state. The district has a rich heritage and history and is a popular tourist destination as well.

Source: Internet

Materials and Methods

This consisted of the collection of secondary data and information from various sources. Secondary data was collected from Census reports, District Handbooks, journal, websites and books. The disparity in education is calculated by Sopher's Index (1974):

$$\text{Sopher's Disparity Index} = D = \log(X_2 / X_1) + \log\{(100 - X_1) / (100 - X_2)\}$$

Objective of the Study

The major objectives of the study are-

- To identify the gender gap in literacy in the CD Blocks of Malda
- To assess the quantitative aspect of it
- To identify the contributing factors
- To suggest measures for improvement of the situation

The Gender Gap in Literacy

Malda district is composed of fifteen CD Blocks which fall under the two sub divisions of the district: Malda Sadar and Chanchal. Nine CD Blocks, namely, Gazole, Bamangola, Habibpur, Old Malda, English Bazar, Manikchak, Kaliachak-I, Kaliachak-II and Kaliachak-III fall under Malda Sadar. Six CD Blocks are under the Chanchal sub division, namely, Harishchandrapur-I, Harishchandrapur-II, Chanchal-I, Chanchal-II, Ratua-I and Ratua-II. Eight of the CD Blocks are having urban population while others only constitute of rural population. According to the Census 2011, the literacy rate in the district is 61.73 with a gender gap of 9.68. male literacy rate is 66.24 and female literacy rate is 56.96 in the district.

Table 1: Literacy Rate and Gender Gap in Male and Female Literates

Sl No	CD Block	Male Literacy Rate (%)	Female Literacy Rate (%)	Literacy Gap
1	Harishchandrapur I	57.37	47.21	10.16
2	Harishchandrapur II	57.21	51.23	5.98
3	Chanchal I	68.39	60.85	7.54
4	Chanchal II	59.97	54.66	5.31
5	Ratua I	64.17	55.81	8.36
6	Ratua II	58.31	53.98	4.33
7	Gazole	69.00	55.03	13.97
8	Bamangola	75.52	60.20	15.32
9	Habibpur	64.05	47.35	16.70
10	Malda Old	63.65	51.83	11.82
11	Englishbazar	67.21	59.10	8.11
12	Manikchak	64.18	50.89	13.29
13	Kaliachak I	66.71	60.20	6.51
14	Kaliachak II	69.86	60.13	9.73
15	Kaliachak III	59.54	47.61	11.93

Source: District Census Handbook, Malda, 2011

The table depicts that literacy rate is overall low in the concerned district with a huge gap in literacy between male and female. Kaliachak II records the highest male literacy of 69.86 and Chanchal I records the highest female literacy of 60.85. The lowest literacy rates of male are observed in Harishchandrapur II (57.21) and that of females are observed in Harishchandrapur I (47.21). the gender gap in

literacy is pronounced in Habibpur (16.70) followed by Bamangola (15.32) and Gazole (13.97).

The Disparity Index

The disparity in male-female population of the blocks is calculated by means of Sopher Index. This shows the regions where disparity is quite prominent in relation to other blocks of the district.

Table 2: Disparity in Literate Population by Sopher Index

Sl No	CD Blocks	Male Literates (%)	Female Literates (%)	A=Log(X ₂ /X ₁)	B=Log(100-X ₁ /100-X ₂)	S.I (A+B)
1	Harishchandrapur I	57.37	47.21	0.085	0.085	0.17
2	Harishchandrapur II	57.21	51.23	0.047	0.047	0.094
3	Chanchal I	68.39	60.85	0.051	0.051	0.102
4	Chanchal II	59.97	54.66	0.040	0.040	0.08
5	Ratua I	64.17	55.81	0.060	0.060	0.12

6	Ratua II	58.31	53.98	0.033	0.033	0.066
7	Gazole	69.00	55.03	0.098	0.098	0.196
8	Bamangola	75.52	60.20	0.098	0.098	0.196
9	Habibpur	64.05	47.35	0.131	0.131	0.262
10	Malda Old	63.65	51.83	0.089	0.089	0.178
11	Englishbazar	67.21	59.10	0.056	0.056	0.112
12	Manikchak	64.18	50.89	0.100	0.100	0.20
13	Kaliachak I	66.71	60.20	0.045	0.045	0.09
14	Kaliachak II	69.86	60.13	0.065	0.065	0.13
15	Kaliachak III	59.54	47.61	0.097	0.097	0.194

Source: Computed by Author

High Disparity Zone: High disparity in literacy among male and female is found in the CD Blocks of Bamangola, Habibpur, Manikchak, Kaliachak III, Gazole, Harishchandrapur I.

Moderate Disparity Zone: Moderate disparity in educational status are mostly found in the blocks of Chanchal I, Ratua I, Old Malda, Kaliachak II, Englishbazar.

Low Disparity Zone: Low disparity of literacy is found in Harishchandrapur II, Ratua II, Kaliachak I, Chanchal II.

Factors Contributing to the Disparity

It has been a trend in most parts of our country that a huge disparity exists between the educational attainment of male and females. Malda is no exception. The causes are deep rooted in the society which is a patriarchal one. Girls are mostly moulded to do the household chores to be better suited for the roles of daughters, wives and mothers. Malda has a very high drop out rate of girls who discontinue education after attaining the primary or the secondary level. Added to this are the class bias, religious barriers in attainment of education and untouchability. In many of the blocks, the primary and secondary schools are nearby, but the college and universities are far away from the villages. The safety of the female students becomes a question which the families are not willing to bargain. Thus, the education attended by them mostly gets restricted to school level. Household income always has a direct correlation with education. Most of the BPL families are unable and unwilling to send their daughters to school. Muslims contribute nearly 51.27% of the population in Malda (2011). The religious beliefs of some households, in many cases, acts as a barrier for women to attain higher education. The highest status accorded to marriage and motherhood in many communities' impacts negatively on female participation in education. The presence of female teachers sometimes affects the attendance rate in schools for the girls. The families with certain cultural beliefs feel comfortable when female teachers

are available in schools which the female students are attending. More or less the students after dropping out from upper primary classes were helping the parents in earning the money, either by getting them involved in the agriculture or other activities to earn money.

Suggested Measures

Education means to spread the light of knowledge to every corner of the society. But Malda presents a gloomy picture of reality. Gender gap in education is a long-talked issue in this region. Though several attempts have been made by the Central and State governments, yet the disparity prevails. Certain measures can be undertaken to include female in the mainstream education system. Apart from the existing system, vocational training courses must be introduced in schools according to the student strengths to prevent the dropout rates. Several programmes have been initiated by the governments but a clear observation of the socio-economic background of the villages must be taken into account for implementation of these plans. For enhancing accessibility to school the content of the school curriculum must be strong. Moreover, communication and transport facilities must be taken care of. Adult education plays a pivotal role here. Educated parents will feel the urge to educate their children irrespective of the gender. Thus, adult education centres and community awareness schemes must be present in the villages. The cumulative effect of all these factors when properly implemented can bring about positive results in the transformation of the society.

Conclusion

Education of women plays a pivotal role in women empowerment and narrowing gender gap. The literacy picture in India and in more or less every state of it shows a scenario where females stagger behind men in education. The social and economic scenario of our patriarchal society does not boost or motivate women in most cases to complete higher education. A huge pool of human resource goes unidentified and

unutilised in this way. In Malda, women are found to be economically poor. They are discriminated and marginalised at every level of society whether it is economic participation, social participation, political participation, access to education and also reproductive healthcare. They need economic power to stand on their own with men. This primarily requires similar education trend with that of men. However, the literacy gap between the genders marks the gap between their empowerment status. Corrective decisions are to be taken for the overall collective growth of the nation which requires to learn about the participation of males and females in the economy. Education thus remains the basic tool for a woman to take life changing decisions for herself and the society.

Reference

1. Development and Planning Department (2007): District
2. Human Development Report; Malda, Government of
3. West Bengal, Kolkata
4. Development and Planning Department, (2007) District Human Development Report, Malda, Government of West Bengal.
5. District Census Handbook, Maldah, Census of West Bengal, (2011), Series 20, Part XIII.
6. Govinda R, & Mathew A, (2018), Universalization of Elementary Education In India- Story of Missed Targets and Unkept Promises, Council For Social Development, New Delhi, pp 20-25
7. Jansson Bruce S, (2012), Reducing Inequality, Cognella Academic Publishing, pp 212-215.
8. Kerr K, Dyson A, Raffo C,(2006), Education, Disadvantage and Place, Bristol University Press, pp 135-160.
9. Mayabi C (2016), The Role of Education in Fighting Inequality, Grin Publishing, pp 36-42.
10. Potts P, (2002), Equality and Diversity in Education 1: Experiences of Learning, Teaching and Managing Schools, Brunner-Routledge Publication, pp 123-144.
11. Robertson M, Blackstone T, Lodge P, (2011), Educational Policy and Educational Inequality, Lodge and Blakst, pp 15-22.
12. United Nations Development Programme, (2019), Human Development Report, 2019, Oxford University Press, New York.